

BOND BEHAVIOR BETWEEN FRCM AND MASONRY: A COMPARISON BETWEEN SINGLE-LAP AND TENSILE TESTS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM) composites offer effective reinforcement for masonry structures. The aim of the present investigation was to evaluate the bond behavior between a carbon fiber FRCM and a masonry substrate. A total of 17 single-lap tests are presented. The FRCM had a width of 100 mm and variable bonded length. Load responses are reported together with a discussion of the failure modes in relation to the type of brick and bonded length used. In addition, two clevis-grip tensile tests were conducted on FRCM coupons made with the same FRCM system and results are discussed and compared with those of single-lap tests.

KEYWORDS

Bond; Fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM); Masonry; Clevis-grip tensile test; Single-lap test

INTRODUCTION

Masonry structures are prevalent across Europe and worldwide, encompassing a significant number of heritage buildings. These structures require preservation measures to mitigate the risks posed by natural disasters, deterioration, and human factors. Historical masonry buildings possess inherent vulnerability to seismic actions (Cannizzaro et al., 2017; Castellazzi et al., 2013; D'Altri et al., 2017; Fiorentino et al., 2018; Valente et al., 2017) leading to potential partial or complete collapse, stemming from a combination of factors, including their unique construction techniques, historical alterations, material deterioration over time, and other contributing elements. To safeguard masonry structures from earthquake-induced damage or disruption, the utilization of externally bonded composites has become a common practice. Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) and fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM) composites are frequently employed to enhance the flexural and shear capacity of masonry panels, increase the load-carrying capacity of vaults and domes, and improve the seismic resilience of masonry structures (ACI 440, 2017; CNR, 2020).

FRP materials offer notable advantages, including their lightweight nature, high strength and stiffness, corrosion resistance, application flexibility, and rapid installation. However, FRPs do possess a significant drawback associated with their durability. The organic resins used in the FRP matrix are susceptible to aging caused by environmental factors such as moisture, UV radiation, oxygen, and temperature variations (Ghiassi et al., 2016; Maljaee et al., 2016; Sciolti et al., 2012). To address this durability limitation, composite strengthening systems based on inorganic matrices have been introduced. Usually referred to as FRCM composites (Babaeidarabad et al., 2014; Papanicolaou et al., 2007; Van Balen & Verstrynghe, 2016), these systems comprise fiber open-mesh fabrics embedded in an inorganic matrix, which can be cement- or lime-based. The fibers commonly employed include carbon, steel, basalt, glass, or polyparaphenylene benzobisoxazole. The use of an inorganic matrix in FRCM composite helps overcome certain drawbacks associated with FRPs. The cementitious matrix can be applied onto irregular substrates, is less susceptible to aging, and maintains permeability to water and water vapor. In technical literature, these composite materials are commonly referred to by various acronyms such as TRM (Textile Reinforced Mortar) (Harajli et al., 2010; Papanicolaou et al., 2007), CMG (Cementitious Matrix-Grid system) (Lignola et al., 2009; Prota et al., 2006), IMG (Inorganic Matrix Grid system) (Parisi et al., 2011), CFCM (Carbon Fiber Cement Matrix) (Kolsch,

1998), TRC (Textile Reinforced Concrete) (Banholzer et al., 2006; Ortlepp et al., 2006), MBC (Mineral Based Composites) (Blanksvård et al., 2009), or FRC (Fiber Reinforced Cement) (Wu & Sun, 2005).

The debonding of the FRCM composite from the supporting surface is the primary cause of collapse in structural elements strengthened with externally bonded reinforcement (EBR) (D'Ambrisi & Focacci, 2011). The premature detachment occurring at the interface between the FRCM composite and the masonry undermines the complete utilization of the strengthening system. (Askouni & Papanicolaou, 2019; Bakis C. E. et al., 2002; Carloni et al., 2017; de Felice et al., 2021). Hence, characterization of the bond between the FRCM composite and the masonry is of utmost importance. Being a relatively new material in the field of structural strengthening, research on stress transfer between fibers and the masonry in FRCM strengthened structural element has been less prevalent in the existing literature (Carozzi et al., 2017; D'Ambrisi et al., 2013). Recent experimental studies have highlighted distinct characteristics of the bond between FRCM composites and masonry compared to the bond observed in FRP materials (D'Ambrisi et al., 2013). While the debonding surface in FRP materials is typically located within the supporting material, different debonding mechanisms are observed in FRCM composites, which also involve the fiber-matrix and matrix-substrate interface (Carozzi et al., 2014; De Felice et al., 2020). These observations emphasize the need for further investigation and understanding of the bond behavior in FRCM composites (Harajli et al., 2010; Ortlepp et al., 2006).

This study presents an experimental work to evaluate the bond characteristics between a cement-based matrix, reinforced with a unidirectional carbon fiber fabric, and three specific clay brick masonry configurations. The assessment was performed through single-lap shear tests, considering different bonded lengths (ℓ). Additionally, clevis-grip tensile tests were performed to evaluate the tensile mechanical properties of the FRCM composite coupon (Arboleda et al., 2016; Donnini et al., 2016; Focacci et al., 2022). Both the single-lap shear test and the clevis-grip tensile test were mandated for evaluating the performance of the FRCM system according to the US ACI 549.6R-20 (ACI 549.4 R-20, 2020) and Italian CNR-DT 215/2018 (CNR, 2020) guidelines. The assessment encompasses the analysis of both tensile and bond properties. In addition, the discussion will also explore the analogy between the single-lap shear test and the clevis-grip tensile test. The experimental test procedure, along with the main results, will be illustrated, and the influence of various experimental parameters will be discussed.

MATERIALS

In order to conduct single-lap shear tests and investigate the bond between the FRCM composite and different masonry surfaces, three distinct types of clay brick masonry were used. The objective behind employing various brick types was to examine any potential influence on the bond between the surface of the masonry and the FRCM composite, a critical factor in determining failure. The three brick types used (Figure 1) were as follows: 1) Watsontown red paver brick (WT) (Figure 1b); 2) Belden belcrest 500 (B500) (Figure 1c); and 3) Reclaimed (used) bricks that may have chipping and occasional paint (UB) (Figure 1d). WT bricks provide a smooth and flat surface, exhibiting considerably lower porosity in contrast to B500 bricks, which are face bricks and primarily employed in constructions. A standard mortar mix, commonly employed in construction, was used to fabricate the masonry blocks.

The FRCM composite used in this experimental study consisted of a unidirectional carbon grid embedded within a cementitious matrix. The carbon grid featured coated carbon fiber yarns spaced 17 mm on center (Figure 1a), with an equivalent fiber thickness (t_f) (in the longitudinal direction) of 0.157 mm (CSS-UCG, 2018). The carbon fiber yarns were held together by transversal glass fiber yarns spaced at 31 mm on center. The cementitious matrix is reinforced with polypropylene fibers. The carbon grid was impregnated and bonded to the masonry blocks using the cementitious matrix. The tensile modulus of the cured composite is 49 GPa (CSS-UCG, 2018).

Table 1 provides the mechanical and geometrical properties of both the carbon grid and the cementitious matrix taken from the manufacturer data sheets (CSS-CM, 2019; CSS-UCG, 2018).

Figure 1: Materials used for the construction of the specimens

Table 1: Mechanical and geometrical properties of the carbon grid and the cementitious matrix

Material	Tensile strength (MPa)	Failure tensile strain	Splitting tensile strength (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Compressive strength at 28 days (MPa)
Unidirectional fiber	2866	1.5%	-	-	-
Cementitious matrix	-	-	4.8	6.9	52

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TEST SETUP

The objective of the test campaign was to examine the bond behavior between the FRCM composite and fire-clay brick masonry. Furthermore, the study aimed to determine whether failure occurred at the fiber-matrix interface or elsewhere. A total of 17 masonry blocks were utilized to apply the FRCM, which had three different bonded lengths (300, 200, and 100 mm) to assess the influence of this parameter on the debonding force. The width of the FRCM (B_f) was set at 100 mm. The nominal dimensions of the bricks were 90 mm in width and 50 mm in height, while the mortar joints had a thickness of 7 mm. To construct the masonry blocks, six bricks and five mortar joints were arranged in a stretch and header pattern. Prior to construction, all bricks were soaked in water for a minimum of 24 hours. After allowing the mortar joints to cure for seven days, the masonry blocks were secured with a plastic strap to prevent any separation or damage during handling. The application of FRCM to the masonry blocks took place at least 14 days after casting the masonry blocks. For casting the three different bonded lengths (ℓ) of FRCM, three distinct sizes of 3D printed plastic molds were employed. The cementitious matrix was prepared in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations. Initially, a 3 mm thick layer of the cementitious matrix was applied onto the masonry block only on the bonded area. Subsequently, carbon fiber fabric was placed on the matrix layer. The length of the fabric was such that it extended beyond the bonded area by 50 mm at the free end and 375 mm at the loaded end (Figure 2a). Finally, another 3 mm thick layer of the cementitious matrix was applied on top of the laid carbon fiber. The total thickness of the FRCM composite was 6.4 mm. In a preliminary study, the authors have also investigated a larger thickness (12.7 mm) of FRCM composite; however, it was found that the bond behavior was not affected by the thickness of the FRCM at least in the range considered. The FRCM was subjected to moist curing for 14 days before conducting the single-lap shear tests. The bonded area started 25 mm from the edge of the masonry block (Figure 2a) to avoid any damage to the corner portion of the block during the single-lap shear tests. Two FRCM composite coupons were cast by employing the same carbon fiber and cementitious matrix. The coupons were fabricated with dimensions of 625 mm length, 75 mm width, and 13 mm thickness. The coupons were subjected to a similar moist curing process as previously described.

For the single-lap shear test, two aluminum tabs measuring 100 mm by 50 mm were glued to both sides of the carbon fiber at the loaded end. These tabs facilitated gripping in the servo-hydraulic testing machine. A tensile force (F) was applied using the machine head, which gripped onto the aluminum tabs (Figure 2a).

Figure 2: Single-lap shear and clevis-grip test setup

The specimen was positioned on a steel plate connected to the machine base, while another steel plate was placed on top of the masonry block to restrict any movement. These two plates were connected by four bolted rods. To measure the relative displacement between the FRCM and the masonry surface, two vertical LVDTs (linear variable displacement transformers) were installed at the start of the FRCM-masonry bonded area (Figure 2a). The average reading from these two LVDTs is referred to as the global slip (g), while the displacement recorded by the testing machine is denoted as the stroke (D). Initially, the test was conducted in stroke control mode at a rate of 0.005 mm/s. If the LVDTs had displayed consistent readings in terms of sign and magnitude, the remaining portion of the test until failure was controlled by the average of the two LVDT readings, maintaining a rate of 0.00084 mm/s. However, if the LVDT readings were inconsistent, the test proceeded in stroke control mode until failure. The rate of the test using the LVDTs was selected to ensure a stroke rate of approximately 0.005 mm/s. Table 2 shows the mode of control used to run the tests. The coupon tests were conducted in accordance with the AC434 (ICC-ES, 2016) guidelines. Two steel plates were epoxy-glued to each end of the coupon. The grip length (L_g), representing the bonded length of each plate, was set at 250 mm, while the free length (L_f) was 125 mm (Figure 2b). Two LVDTs were used to measure the displacement within this free length (L_f). A clevis-type joint was affixed to the steel plates at both ends to allow unrestricted rotation. The coupons were subjected to a tensile force (F) in a stroke control mode, with a rate of 0.005 mm/s.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 17 single-lap shear tests and two clevis-grip tensile tests were conducted to examine the bond behavior between FRCM and masonry. The findings, presented in this section, depict the relationship between axial stress (σ_f) and strain (ϵ_f) for single-lap shear tests. The axial stress σ_f was computed as the ratio of the tensile force and the fiber fabric cross-sectional area:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{F}{t_f B_f} \quad (1)$$

The strain (ϵ_f) was determined by dividing the machine stroke (D) by the length of the bare fibers at the loaded end (i.e. 375 mm). Table 2 provides the maximum stress ($\sigma_{f,max}$) derived from each single-lap shear, and the average maximum stress $\bar{\sigma}_{f,max}$ with the coefficient of variation (CoV) for each group of bonded lengths. Table 2 also shows if the specimen failed by FRCM-masonry detachment or rupture of the fiber. The single-lap shear test specimens were named using the notation X_L_Y_Z, where X represents the brick type (WT, B500, and UB), L indicates the bonded length (ℓ) of the FRCM composite, Y represents the failure mode, and Z denotes the specimen number within the same group of specimens with the same brick type and bonded length. The specimens that failed due to the tensile failure of the fiber have ‘f’ in their name and the specimens that failed by the detachment of the composite from the masonry have ‘d’ in their name. Some masonry blocks had a thin layer of residual mortar used for jointing, originating from the construction process. Moreover, certain masonry blocks exhibited non-planar surfaces. Specimens having these deficiencies are marked with an asterisk (*) at the end of their name in Table 2.

Table 2: Specimen bonded lengths, peak stress, and failure modes for single-lap shear tests

Specimen name	ℓ (mm)	Test control mode	$\sigma_{f,max}$ (MPa)	Failure mode	$\bar{\sigma}_{f,max}$ (MPa)(CoV)
WT_300_f_1	300	LVDTs	1137	Fiber rupture	1054 6.8%
WT_300_f_2	300	LVDTs	1064	Fiber rupture	
WT_300_f_3	300	LVDTs	962	Fiber rupture	
WT_300_d_4*	300	LVDTs	897	Detachment	937 6.8%
WT_300_f_5*	300	LVDTs	886	Fiber rupture	
WT_300_d_6*	300	LVDTs	1028	Detachment	
B500_300_d_1	300	LVDTs	1067	Detachment	873 18.7%
B500_300_d_2	300	LVDTs	666	Detachment	
B500_300_f_3	300	LVDTs	886	Fiber rupture	
UB_300_d_1	300	Stroke	541	Detachment	754 40.1%
UB_300_f_2	300	Stroke	1182	Fiber rupture	
UB_300_d_3	300	Stroke	539	Detachment	
WT_200_d_1*	200	Stroke	348	Detachment	622 71.3%
WT_200_d_2*	200	Stroke	270	Detachment	
WT_200_f_3*	200	LVDTs	1248	Fiber rupture	
WT_100_d_1*	100	Stroke	102	Detachment	400
WT_100_d_2*	100	LVDTs	698	Detachment	

Influence of bonded length and surface preparation using brick type “WT”

The responses of the single-lap shear tests of specimens constructed using WT bricks are illustrated in Figure 3a and b, depicting the stress (σ_f) versus the global slip (g) and the stress (σ_f) versus the strain (ϵ_f), respectively. The $\sigma_f - g$ responses (Figure 3a) exhibited consistency among different bonded length groups, excluding WT_300_f_5*. Initially, the $\sigma_f - g$ responses displayed a linear behavior followed by a non-linear response prior to fiber rupture or detachment at the FRCM-masonry interface. Conversely, specimens experiencing premature detachment (WT_200_d_1*, WT_200_d_2*, and WT_100_d_1*) did not exhibit any discernible non-linear behavior in the latter stages of the response and were associated with comparatively lower stress values. Notably, WT_300_f_5* demonstrated higher initial stiffness compared to other specimens. The $\sigma_f - \epsilon_f$ responses in Figure 3b also shows consistent results. The strain (ϵ_f) was linear for all the specimens (except WT_300_f_5*) as the stress (σ_f) increased and finally the specimens failed by either detachment or rupture of the fiber. The tests on different bonded lengths (ℓ) show that the tensile failure of the fiber can be achieved even with a bonded length of 200 mm (see WT_200_f_3* in

Figure 3). Some masonry blocks (as the one shown in Figure 2a) were characterized by a thin layer of residual mortar and exhibited non-planar surfaces

Figure 3: Single-lap shear test results for specimens with WT bricks and different bonded lengths of FRCM

These masonry blocks underwent additional preparation, including the removal of any mortar layer from the joints and meticulous efforts to achieve a flat masonry surface. Figure 4a and b present the $\sigma_f - g$ and $\sigma_f - \epsilon_f$ responses, respectively, for the WT bricks with a bonded length (ℓ) of 300 mm, both with and without the identified deficiencies. Notably, the specimens without deficiencies uniformly experienced fiber rupture as the failure mode. Furthermore, these specimens exhibited slightly higher maximum stress levels compared to the specimens with deficiencies.

Figure 4: Single-lap shear test results of specimens with and without deficiencies, $\ell = 300$ mm

Influence of the type of brick on single-lap shear tests

Figure 5a and b present the $\sigma_f - g$ and $\sigma_f - \epsilon_f$ responses, respectively, for three distinct brick types with a FRCM bonded length of 300 mm. The $\sigma_f - g$ responses exhibited similarities to the previously discussed responses. Notably, no significant differences were observed among specimens with the

three brick types when failure of the fibers occurred, although detachment was observed for some specimens with B500 and UB bricks.

Figure 5: Single-lap shear test results for specimens with three different brick types, $\ell = 300$ mm

It is important to mention that the WT bricks exhibited a smoother and flatter surface compared to the B500 and UB bricks. As a result, it can be inferred that masonry blocks constructed with WT bricks offer improved planarity compared to those built with the other two brick types. This suggests that planarity can be considered as one of the various factors influencing the bond between the matrix and substrate. In addition, the reclaimed bricks did not have a regular surface and had residue of paint that might have affected the bond between the matrix and the brick.

Discussion on single-lap shear test results

No indications of full debonding at the fiber-matrix interface were observed across any of the specimens. In most commercially available FRCM systems, failure at the fiber-matrix interface typically occurs at stress levels ranging from 30% to 75% of the fiber tensile strength (De Felice et al., 2020). Exploiting the full tensile strength of the fiber is essential in FRCM composites that employ specific fiber types. The rupture of the fiber (Figure 6a) occurred at different stress levels among different specimens. This occurrence can be attributed to variations in stress distribution among the fibers within the yarn and uneven loading of the yarns. Such behavior is an inherent characteristic of FRCMs, observed even in full-scale applications, due to the diverse stress transfer mechanisms between each yarn and the matrix. Complete detachment of the entire FRCM composite from the masonry substrate (as depicted in Figure 6b) was observed for some specimens and part was attributed to the presence of mortar during the construction of the masonry blocks or to the irregular surface of the bricks. It is also possible that the FRCM was not properly applied to the masonry blocks. In certain regions of the bonded area, a thin layer of mortar was found attached to the matrix (as shown in Figure 6c). Premature detachment of the FRCM-masonry bond did not exhibit a direct correlation with the surface quality of the masonry block. Neither the presence of a thin layer of mortar in the joints nor the lack of planarity in the masonry blocks could be solely attributed to the premature detachment, as fiber failure occurred in specimens featuring either or both of these deficiencies.

Three-point bending tests of the FRCM strips from single-lap shear tests

The results of the single-lap shear tests demonstrated that there was no apparent reason for the differing behavior of certain specimens in terms of their failure mechanisms. In order to gain a deeper understanding of the bond behavior, additional tests were conducted on completely detached FRCM strips using a three-point bending (TPB) configuration to investigate their flexural behavior. The details of the test configuration can be found in (Rahman et al., 2022).

Specimens designated as WT_300_d_4* and WT_300_d_6* experienced failure due to detachment of the FRCM strips. These detached strips were subsequently collected, and any protruding fiber were cut off. The span of the FRCM strip was 250 mm. Flexural tests were then conducted on these FRCM strips in a flat configuration (Figure 7a), and the results of these tests, in terms of the applied force (P) and stroke (D), are depicted in Figure 7b.

Figure 6: Failure modes of the single-lap shear test specimens

Fracture of the FRCM strips occurred at the mid-span location. The observed softening behavior exhibited characteristics consistent with the typical response of quasibrittle materials (Rahman et al., 2022). WT_300_d_6* demonstrated a higher peak compared to WT_300_d_4* during the flexural tests. Though it is not possible to establish a correlation between the flexural tests of the FRCM strips and the single-lap shear tests of the strip, the consistent initial response of the flexural tests suggest that the FRCM strips were cast properly and the detachment of the strip is associated with matrix-substrate interface. Further investigation is still required to explore this aspects in more detail.

Figure 7: Flexural test setup and response on FRCM strips received from single lap shear tests

Clevis-grip tensile tests of FRCM composite coupons

Two clevis-grip tensile tests were conducted using the same fiber and matrix employed in the single-lap shear tests. The test specimens were labeled as C_Q_R, wherein C indicated the clevis-grip test, Q represented the free length (L_f), and R denoted the number of the specimen. Figure 8a illustrates the stress (σ_f) versus strain (ϵ_f) results obtained from these clevis-grip tests. In addition, Figure 8a also shows the tensile test of the bare carbon grid to compare it with the clevis-grip tensile tests. This carbon grid was cut off from WT_200_d_1* bare fibers between the machine grip and the start of the matrix-substrate bond after the single-lap test was completed. Stress values were calculated using Eq. (1). For clevis-grip tests, strain values were determined by averaging the measurements of the two LVDTs and dividing the average elongation obtained by the free length (L_f). The LVDT holder was mounted at the edge of the steel plate and the LVDT reacted against a plate mounted at the edge of the other steel plate. For the bare fiber test, the stroke of the machine was divided by the gauge length (250 mm) to obtain the strain. The responses depicted in Figure 8a exhibited consistency among them. The clevis-grip test $\sigma_f - \epsilon_f$ responses displayed an initial brief linear section, followed by kinks (C_125_2) or changes in slope (C_125_1) indicating matrix cracking. Subsequently, the fibers were carrying the load with tension stiffening effect between the cracks in the matrix, which was associated with a non-linear response until the peak stress was reached, at which point the fibers fractured (Figure 8b). Typically, matrix cracks were observed near edges of the steel plates, i.e., at the ends of the free length (L_f), and an additional crack was observed in the middle of the free length (Figure 8b). Comparing the peak stresses in Figure 8a with those shown in Figure 5b for the single-lap shear test specimens, where fiber rupture was the failure mode, it can be observed that the peak stresses attained in these two types of tests were quite similar. Furthermore, the bare fiber tension test in Figure 8a shows similar kind of peak stress. Hence, it can be concluded that the clevis-grip tests closely resemble single-lap shear tests with fiber rupture as the failure mode. When debonding between the FRCM and the substrate does not occur, and the fiber-matrix interface is the critical one, clevis-grip tests can be used to study the fiber-matrix bond behavior as suggested from the results herein presented. The peak stresses obtained from clevis-grip tensile tests and the bare fiber tensile test in Figure 8a indicate lower strength of the grid compared to the one reported in Table 1. However, the manufacturer's technical sheet (CSS-UCG, 2018) does not provide information on the test sample specifics, such as the carbon filament or yarn. In single-lap and tensile tests, even distribution of the stress among the yarns is hardly achieved, since stress is transferred from the matrix to the fibers. Thus it is expected that stress concentration in one of ore yarns occurs and the average stress at which the fibers fail is less than the actual tensile strength.

Figure 8: Clevis-grip test results and failed specimen (C_125_2)

CONCLUSIONS

A total of 17 specimens underwent single-lap shear tests, consisting of three different types of bricks, various bonded lengths, and masonry block surface conditions. Two primary failure modes, fiber rupture and FRCM detachment from the masonry substrate, were examined through analysis of the obtained test results. Notably, no failure occurred at the fiber-matrix interface. The investigation of different bonded lengths revealed that a 200 mm bond length fully exploited the tensile strength of the fibers. The detachment of the composite material might have influenced by several factors, including but not limited to the presence of thin mortar layer on the masonry surface from mortar joints, planarity irregularities in the masonry surface, and the use of reclaimed bricks that had paint residue. These factors might have played a role in the observed detachment failures and impacted the bonding performance. Further investigation is needed to understand the effect of different brick types. Flexural tests conducted on detached FRCM strips yielded contradictory outcomes when compared to the single-lap shear tests, but drawing conclusive findings was challenging due to the limited number of tests. Thus, additional investigation is required for better comprehension of these inconsistencies. Additionally, clevis-grip tests were performed using the same fiber and matrix. The peak stresses obtained from these tests were similar to those from the single-lap shear tests for specimens that failed due to fiber rupture. This observation confirms that when the fiber-matrix interface is the one that is activated, the single-lap shear tests are comparable to tensile tests. Consequently, using tensile tests could reduce the testing efforts required to investigate this bond behavior.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

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